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Deliverable 1.5

Promotion of photonics at 5 Children's Universities – final feedback report

Deliverable Name	Promotion of photonics at 5 Children's Universities – final feedback report
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1. Introduction

Definition ‘Children Universities’: events offering workshops & lectures for children during their holidays. The workshops and lectures include experiments, competition activities and educational games. The University of Southampton (UoS), Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum (SEZ), Photonics Sweden (EaPS) and Photonics Austria (PhAu) incorporated the use of educational tools, in the Children’s Universities which had been developed as part of the Photonics4all project; i.e. app, video, quiz, game etc. and the Photonics Explorer Kit of Eyest_{vzw}. Some partners took part in regional existing ‘Children Universities’ in Germany, Austria and Sweden increasing the awareness of photonics for the youngest ‘researchers’. The aim of the Children Universities was to try to familiarize school children, teenagers and their parents with the term ‘Photonics’ and of the importance of Photonics in our lives. School children were encouraged to engage with photonics to build on their existing knowledge of science and technology.

Objective of this document: summarize the organisation, implementation and impact of all Photonics4All children’s universities. The project consortium conducted 9 children’s universities in five countries during the two years of the project. This fact comprises thus a wide variety of organisations efforts, local specificities and individual impacts. With this paper, we try to demonstrate the diversity of particular activities on the one hand. On the other hand, the global, equally achieved impact on the awareness of children for photonics is explained.

2. Methodology of Impact Assessment

In our original Photonics4All proposal we listed the number of Children’s University events we would do, the number of children we hoped to reach and our proposed evaluation was limited to collecting the quantitative data from the number of events and participants. Four Photonics4All partners from four different countries planned to reach at least 100 children (plus their parents and siblings to increase impact) in order to engage a total of at least 400 children with photonics.

In the Description of Action between the Commission and the consortium no qualitative assessment of the Children’s University was described or even mentioned. Nevertheless, in response to the criticisms of our project Reviewers a qualitative evaluation scheme was developed during the project. The consortium felt that it was necessary to understand the learning outcomes of the activities for the children to better understand the needs of the participants, partners, and for the purposes of best practice.

Different partners had different concepts of Children Universities both in terms of existing event structure and age group of participant. Pearl John, from the University of Southampton (UoS), conducted a knowledge transfer workshop, to discuss shared

event aims and suitable methods of evaluation at the second partner meeting in Como (Italy) in June 2015. A short excerpt of the most important aspects can be found below:

Children's Universities
Do we have shared Measurable Objectives for our events?
What activities are we running?
What are our learning objectives for those activities?
How will we evaluate the success, or the Impact of the Children's Universities?
Will the events be good value for money?

What is Impact?

The Impact of a public engagement activity is:

Reach x Significance
(largest numbers possible) x (how transformative is the activity)

What do we need to measure?	
Quantitative Data	Qualitative Data
Reach: How many students are we working with (male and female)?	Significance: how transformative is the activity?
How many teachers or parents are accompanying the students?	Change in knowledge – what has the student learnt?
What age-group are the students?	Change in attitude – are the students more interested in Photonics?
Is it truly 'Photonics4All'? Are our students from all backgrounds including those students from disadvantaged backgrounds?	Change in Behaviour – are the students more likely to want to study Photonics, further or go into a Career in Photonics as a result of taking part in the activity?

How do we Gather the data for Evaluation?

Using a variety of methods;

- Freebies,
- postIt notes
- feedback boards
- on-line quizzes,
- social media and competitions

Figure 1 First knowledge transfer workshop UoS

A second knowledge transfer workshop on planning for impact evaluation was given by UoS in Palaiseau (3rd meeting) in December 2015. Below, the template used for planning and evaluating activities can be found. (This plan was based on a Logic Plan developed by the University of Bath and promoted in an Evaluation workshop by the National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement in the UK.) In addition,

partners agreed at the review meeting on 8 April 2016 to strengthen their qualitative impact assessment and follow the planning for evaluation template below:

Physics and Astronomy - Public Engagement Activity Plan

Planning → Intended Results →

Aims and Objectives	INPUTS What is required to achieve aims & objectives eg: human, financial, organisational, community	ACTIVITIES What the project does with the resources; its processes, tools, events, activities and actions	OUTPUTS Direct products of the project eg. types, levels and targets of what will be delivered	OUTCOMES Specific Changes in participant behaviour, knowledge, skills, attitudes and level of functioning	IMPACT The intended or unintended change in organisations, communities or systems as a result of the project

Figure 2 Second knowledge transfer workshop UoS

Event facts			Quantitative evaluation			Qualitative evaluation		
Date	Partner	Event	Age-group	Number of participants	Number of Girls	Amount of Photonics4All budget used (no personnel)	Change in knowledge What have you learned? (Feedback boards, post-it notes, social media...)	Change in attitude – are the students more interested/inspired about Photonics? (Feedback boards, post-it notes, social media...)

Figure 3 Final evaluation template

3. Shared Aims for the Children’s Universities

The following learning aims and objectives were shared by all Partners although they were dependent on the age and ability of those participating:

- the definition of Photonics
- basic light theory to include – reflection refraction total internal reflection diffraction colour, polarization
- How lenses work, focal points, concave and convex lenses
- How a telescope works
- How a spectroscope works
- Applications of Photonics relevant to each Photonics4All partner’s research or industrial focus, e.g. different light sources, lasers and telecommunications, holography, lasers and manufacturing etc.

In total, 4 people from SEZ were involved in preparing and conducting this activity.

What do you think about LIGHT?

Children University at KIT

What is your gender?

What is your age?

What are you interested in?

„the spectrometer to go“

Sources:
1) <http://bwitek.com/spectrometer-part-1-the-slit/>
2) <https://globalleadershipprograms.wordpress.com/2012/08/14/i-have-an-idea-lets-dance-prisma-escuela-de-arte/>

Figure 6 Evaluation Children’s University Karlsruhe, August 2015

The second German Children’s University dedicated to photonics took place over 2 days, 9 & 11 August 2016, again at Karlsruhe Institute of Technology.

This activity targeted children aged between 7 and 14 years. A total of **150 children** took part in Photonics activities at the booth, 60% of who were girls. The event activities and methods of evaluation were informed by the feedback and experienced gained at the previous year’s. The most popular experiments were repeated from the previous year and included the following;

- Spectrometer to Go (see Appendix 1)
- ‘Galileo telescope’,
- ‘Optical data transmission’

Figure 7 Children’s University Karlsruhe, August 2016

SEZ improved its methods of qualitative data collection and prepared several different items to improve its follow-up. Some of the posters used are shown below in Figure 8 which enabled the children to directly write down their responses to the questions:

- What did you learn about the wonderful world of light?
- Later I would like to work with photonics (yes / no / maybe / what is photonics?)

Figure 8 Evaluation Children's University Karlsruhe, August 2016

The evaluation data was collected, analysed and displayed Figure 9 below. The children fed back that the most popular activity was again the hands-on Spectrometer to go. The SEZ workers who staffed the stand noted that children were also interested in using the Photonics Explorer kits to conduct experiments with:

- the optical fibre and LEDs to understand optical data transmission
- coloured filters including red, green, blue, cyan, magenta and yellow
- robust plastic lenses with the focal lengths 30 mm, -30 mm, and 150 mm to build a 'Galileo telescope'
- polarisers
- diffraction gratings

Figure 9 Children’s University Karlsruhe, August 2016, evaluation

At this second event SEZ distributed diffraction grating glasses obtained from SPIE which had been produced to promote the International Year of Light in 2015 (shown above in Figure 7). The glasses proved to be very popular, not only at this Children’s University, but also at events for the general public, such as the UK’s Tatton Park Garden outreach event and at the ICT Conference. Using the glasses at Photonics4All outreach events and promoting SPIE was a good example of how Photonics4All worked with other relevant authorities and organisations.

In total, 3 persons from SEZ were involved in preparing and conducting this activity.

5. Promotion of Photonics at Children’s Universities in Austria

The global initiative *International Year of Light 2015* stimulated the creation of many events and projects to raise the awareness for the achievements of light science. The European project *Photonics4all* aimed to emphasise the importance of photonics and light technologies to professionals, the general public and to young people. In Graz, Austria, two workshops on light and colour were performed for pupils as part of an

existing *Children's University* program. The workshops were organised by *Photonics Austria* and the *University of Graz*¹.

Organisation: Project leaders: Ulrich Trog (Photonics Austria); Workshop leaders: Frank Reil (Joanneum Research), Gernot Schaffernak (University of Graz)

Timetable:

- Two workshops were held at the University of Graz at the Institute of Physics on July, 27th and July, 29th, 2015.
- Two further workshops were held at the University of Graz at the Institute of Physics on September, 26th and September, 27th, 2016.
- Workshop duration was three hours.

Age range & group size: In 2015, the pupils attending the **2 workshops** were aged from 8 to 13 years-old. The **number of pupils per workshop was** small and limited to **11**, which was found to be a suitable number allowing for a pleasant learning environment and a good deal of student/demonstrator interaction.

In 2016, the number of participants doubled. Two school classes attended the workshops, one fourth grade of elementary school and one first grade of gymnasium. The pupils were about 9 to 11 years-old. This time full school classes attended instead of a preselected group of pupils. The **number of pupils per workshop was 20 and 22**, which turned out to be challenging but it was still possible to manage with two workshop leaders who had gained experience in delivering the workshop from the previous year.

Teaching aspects: At the beginning of the workshops, the children were asked what they knew about light and this proved to be good introduction. The children were then put into groups of two or three in order for them to work on activities in the *Photonics Explorer* kit. The two workshop leaders delivered the content in turns to provide some variety in the mediation of the content.

A handout (provided in [Appendix 2](#)) summarizing the covered topics was created and given to the pupils.

List of covered topics

- The sun as most important light source
- The light bulb and other artificial lighting
- Light is fast and can transport information
- Light is propagating as a wave, different colours correspond to different wavelengths
- Explanation of the unit *nanometer*
- Colour perception of the human eye, additive colour mixing: red, green and blue
- Colour filters and inkjet printing, subtractive colour mixing: cyan, magenta and yellow

¹ Third party of Photonics Austria as outlined in GA, page 65.

- Optical grating and spectroscopy
- Optical spectra of different light bulbs: incandescent, energy-saving and LED lamps
- Optical instruments: reading-glass, telescope and microscope
- Usage of a research-grade microscope: study of crystals, flies and computer chips
- Lasers and diffraction
- Structural colour in nature and nanotechnology
- Absorption and scattering of light

Experiments: The performed experiments were based on the *Photonics Explorer* kit. As the experiments in the kit are designed for long sessions, we picked out and combined parts of the documented experiments to fit into our time scale of three hours. In addition, we added own experiments like the *coloured spinning wheel* to demonstrate colour mixing of fast changing colours. We also provided different types of light sources to explain the differences in the optical spectra and extended the content of the *Photonics Explorer* kit with a blue laser to visualize the different scattering properties compared to the red laser. This was essential for the understanding of the blue coloured sky.

Special emphasis was put on the usage of a research-grade optical microscope and the investigation of *small things* together with the pupils. A big LCD screen was connected to the microscope, such that all participants were able to see the magnified images of e.g., a computer chip, a small fly and a pure quartz crystal.

Figure 10 Children's University Graz, 2015

The children's learning was assessed with a quiz at the end of the workshop. Each participant got an optical grating as gift and was encouraged to continue studying the differences of various light sources at home.

Documentation: The initial documentation of the workshops was realized with the German handouts for the participants, summarizing the covered topics with

explanations of the experiments that the children had performed. A more detailed documentation of the workshops is in preparation. This detailed documentation will contain the choice of experiments that fit well into the available workshop time-scale and allow a holistic understanding of light and colour.

Published peer-reviewed scientific article: Find the publication [here](#).

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CHILDREN'S UNIVERSITY: OPTICS AND PHOTONICS FOR CHILDREN

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Abstract

Today, optics and photonics is widely regarded as one of the most important key technologies for this century. Many experts even anticipate that the 21st century will be the century of the photon. Optics and photonics technologies have impact on nearly all areas of our life and cover a wide range of applications in science and industry.

However even so attractive, the photonics is not well known by majority of the people. In order to motivate especially the young generation for the optics and photonics we offered already three times the lecture about "optical data transmission" to the children of age 8-12 years in the frame of Children's University. We prepared many practical activities and experiments to explain how the modern communication through the optical networks works. Combining the hands-on teaching with having a fun while learning about the basic optics concepts we aroused interest of not only the children but also the parents, with a very positive feedback.

Key words: *Children University, optical data transmission, hands-on teaching, basic optics concepts*

Figure 11 Peer-reviewed publication on Children's University, 2015

6. Promotion of Photonics at Children's Universities in the United Kingdom

There is no tradition of, or existing structure for, Children's Universities in the UK, so the UoS designed a specific day-long event of hands-on Photonics activities for **120 students** aged 13-14 years-old, who had to volunteer to attend. This was felt to be in keeping with the informal learning approach of the other partner's Children's University events which were held in the school holidays. As our Children's University day was held late in the Photonics4All project we were able to take advantage of first the experiences of our Photonics4All partners which allowed us to learn from their successes and challenges, secondly, we were able to disseminate age-relevant tools which had been developed as part of the project and thirdly we were able to try out new events, activities and teaching resources at IYL2015 events.

As the UoS had no experience of running a day-long event of Photonics Activities new events were designed and piloted at a number of preceding outreach events in schools and at University. Because the first year of the project was in the International Year of light in 2015 there was a wealth of existing opportunities for us to take part in.

Pilot Activities: Two **laser shows** with photonics talks were given to 210 students visiting the University for Student Award Ceremonies in July 2015 (aged from 14-17 years) from 30 different schools with parents and teachers attending too. Two Photonics talks with accompanying laser shows were given to students and their parents at Thomas Hardy School, Dorset, UK and Cove School, Farnborough, UK in December 2015 as part of STEM Fairs. UoS also included a Photonics show for all visiting students (aged 17-18 years) and their parents, during five University Open Days reaching another 500 people.

With these numerous photonics outreach events for children, UoS reached over **1,700 pupils** during the International Year of Light and Photonics4All project. The UoS also had many opportunities during University schools outreach activities to disseminate photonics tools - even when the subject of the activities not been Photonics.

University of Southampton Photonics Outreach and Public Engagement Activities 2015-2017																			
Staff	Date	Activity	Audience	Town	Post code	KS1	KS2	KS3	KS4	AS & A level	Teachers	Trained Teachers	General Public	University Students	Parents	Total	% of Free School Meals	Evaluation data available?	
						0	0	170	57	597	839	10	4170	32	475	6350	6350		

In the first year of the project, in preparation for the planned Photonics4All Children’s University, the following new outreach activities were designed: a **laser manufacturing and LED activity** (assembling custom-made, laser etched name tags inspired by an activity found on Instructables.com designed by FAB LAB Aachen), a **polarising filter collage workshop** (creative use of collage with polarising filters and tape) and a **‘Mobile Ghost’ activity** – (making a ‘Pepper’s Ghost’ acetate structure for student’s smart phones to create a 3D effect) which can be found in [Appendix 3](#). The Photonics Explorer kit was also used during outreach events (UoS became partners of EYEst during the project and continue to promote the kits to teachers, and generally on social media, to date). To trial the activities with classroom groups two outreach events were held at the University with 13 year-olds and 16 year-olds from two different schools and a further pilot outreach event was held at Havant College with about 20 17-18 year-old students. These pilot projects enabled us to decide what age-group to work with, suitable learning objectives for the age-group and which activities to use. For the greatest impact we decided to work with 13-14 year-olds who would shortly make decisions on whether to study Physics at GCSE - which would in turn affect their choice of A Level subjects and their University careers. We have engaged in a University project which allows us to track the Children’s University students who took part in this event and will be able to find out whether they choose to study Physics at University or not in 5 year’s time.

The piloted activities which were thought to be most successful were shared with consortium members. We also shared different methods of evaluation i.e.: paper and on-line questionnaires (e.g. Kahoot.it) with partners to measure the impact of the events.

The Main Event:

5 Schools from up to one and a half hours away were invited and 126 students attended. The event was held in July 2016.

Ensuring a Diverse Audience: The Children’s University was promoted to young people as ‘Photonics: a day of Art and Science’. This approach was designed to encourage more young women to volunteer to attend; the UK has a problem with science subjects being perceived stereotypically as being relevant only for men, rather than both men and women. The UoS also targeted schools from the inner cities to ensure that students from disadvantaged backgrounds had the opportunity to attend. (We succeeded in having 40% of female students and 3 of the 5 schools were considered to have disadvantaged students).

We used a professional designer to produce the promotional materials for our event shown in Figure 11. We think that the novelty of the event, and the professional promotion approach encouraged the 100% participation we experienced on the day. The University usually experiences a 20% drop out of participants in the couple of days preceding a free outreach event. It was unprecedented to have more students turn up than had applied to come.

Activities:

The following activities were used on the day

- An Interactive Laser Light show
- Spectroscopy and ‘Guess the Gas’
- Hands-on Photonics Explorer Activities
- Mobile Ghosts
- Collage with polarizing filters
- Laser etched name tag assembly
- LightTag – drawing with light and long-exposure photography

Please see Figures 13-18 below which illustrate the above activities.

Figure 12 Children’s University Poster

Figure 14 *Guess the Gas!* Students identify different gases with spectrometers

Figure 18 Students use diffraction gratings to view different light sources during a laser show

Figure 13 *Polage* - the student's favourite activity

Figure 16 *Mobile Ghosts* Pepper's Ghosts with Smart Phones

Figure 15 Students assembled LEDs and batteries to illuminate their laser-etched nametags

Figure 17 *LightTag* students 'draw' with their nametags during long-exposure photographs

To evaluate the impact of the event, participating students, teachers and postgraduate student helpers were all questioned with a paper-based questionnaire to find out what they had learned, what they enjoyed, and whether they had a change in attitude toward studying physics and photonics as a result of the event.

The event was well-received; the students were asked to rate the day out of ten and they gave the day an average rating of 8.4/10.0 and their teachers 9.4/10 in terms of their enjoyment. Most comments given by students indicated that they were well-

engaged with the activities and enjoyed the event. All of the teachers said that they would like to bring students to the event again in 2017 and that they could use what they had learned in the classroom. The event went according to the plan, and each activity ran smoothly, although one of the teaching venues was considered too small by demonstrators and teachers.

Participants were asked “How likely would you be to recommend studying physics or photonics to family and friends?” Initially attendees were not likely to recommend studying physics or photonics however, there was a marked positive change in participants as a result of taking part in the event with a majority of participants stating that they would be very likely to recommend studying physics or photonics after the event.

Figure 19 UoS Evaluation Report

From the students’ questionnaire responses to the question regarding what did you learn? We discovered that what the students learned was very varied; some referred to the science, such as how lasers worked, others recalled applications of laser technology, holography and polarization which had interested them. A thorough evaluation report was made, the recommendations of which will be shared in our ‘Best Practice Guide’. Overall it can be concluded that the event had a good short-term high impact on the attendees and that we had a successful event.

7. Promotion of photonics at children’s universities in Sweden

The Children’s University in Kista, Sweden took place on 1 June 2016. **133 children** participated in this event, aged 6-16 years, among them 47 girls and 86 boys. EaPS used the Photonics4All tools and material from local partners such as PS, Acreo and KTH, the photonics explorer kit, the OSA lightblox kit and conducted several experiments. In total, 26 evaluation questionnaires were filled in by the children. Some impressions of the event can be found in the pictures below.

Figure 20 Some impression about children's universities in Kista, Sweden

Figure 21 Further impression about children's universities in Kista, Sweden

Upptäck Ljus och Elektroner

Figure 22 Poster „Discover Light and Electrons“ developed in Sweden

The 2nd children's university organized in Stockholm, Sweden took place on 30 September 2016 in connection with the "Researcher's Night". 160 children participated in this event. They came in two groups one aged 14-16 years and the other 16-17 years. EaPS used the Photonics4All tools and material from local partners such as PS, Vetenskapens hus and KTH, the Photonics Explorer kit, the OSA lightblox kit and conducted several experiments.

Hamamatsu Photonics Norden AB supported the event with a digital spectrometer for measurement of the intensity of the visible light with a sensitivity from 320nm to 780nm. The spectrometer was borrowed from Hamamatsu.

The demonstration showed the intensity as a function of the wavelength between daylight from the sun, white light generated from Red-Green-Blue LED's, and white LED-light generated from phosphor pumped with a Blue-LED.

This demonstration taught the students how white light could be generated by a LED-TV screen and by their white LED built into their cellphones.

The Photonics App was actively promoted with a big announcement.

Some impressions of the event can be found in the pictures below.

Figure 23 Photographs from Children's Universities in Stockholm, Sweden

To show the impact of the children's universities, we can report that Acreo Swedish ICT AB (research institute) is applying for a project on promoting photonics to girls at the Swedish funding agency Vinnova because the first children's university was so successful and got many positive comments.

8. Promotion of photonics to children at other occasions

Slovakia

The International Laser Center (ILC) was involved in two additional 'Children's Universities', which were not foreseen in the proposal. The events were organized by the University of Cyril and Methodius in Trnava, Slovakia (<http://duc.m.uclm.sk>). The first was held on 9 July 2015 and consisted of the lecture '2015-Year of Light' and interactive session with the support of Photonics4all tools (light painting, colour mixing, lasers and other light sources, see [here](#)). The children's university was attended by two groups / classes of approximately **25 pupils** of age 10-14. The second lecture/workshop about Photonics has been organized on July 8, 2016 and was attended by approx. **50 pupils** (more details available [here](#)).

Besides, a **Student Congress on Photonics** took place in Bratislava, Slovakia in 2015 within the frames of GoPhoton! project, which was joined with the Workshop for teachers organized by Photonics4all and reported in D1.6. The Student congress addressed two age groups of students:

- a) **82 Primary school students** (10-14-years old) on 14th October
- b) **67 Secondary school students** (14-18-years old) on 15th October

The congress was held in the premises of the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information (CVTISR) under the auspices of the Ministry of education, science, research and sport of the Slovak Republic. Students from schools all around Slovakia participated to the event that consisted of two main parts: workshops before noon and presentations of own projects in the afternoon. In the morning students had opportunity to elaborate with various setups, which included opportunity to download mobile phone apps (developed by GoPhoton!), print a 3D object, paint with light, make a solar ship, and play with different aspects of light using Photonics Explorer kit. The workshop continued after lunch by scientific photonics show. In the afternoon, students were given opportunity to present their own projects. From each presenting team, an evaluator was chosen, and - at the end of all presentations - the evaluators voted themselves for the winning presentations. More details and pictures are available at [here](#) - in Slovak).

In 2015 and 2016 the International Laser Centre also organized **annual Open days** (October 19, 2015 and October 21, 2016) related to the Day of Photonics, which were **attended by students and general public** (approx. **35** participants in 2015 and more than **50** in 2016). In both cases visitors highly appreciated possibility to

enter advanced up-to-date scientific labs, as well as discussions with Slovak scientists on photonics, laser technologies, and biophotonics themes.

Figure 24 Activities for children in Slovakia, 2015

Italy

The institute of Photonics and Nanotechnology of the National Research Council (CNR) has done a lot of outreach events for children even though these activities were not conceptually classed as 'children's universities'. CNR has reached approximately **110 children** with the **International Physics Summer School – Optics** (Como, June 2015, 29 children and Olomouc, August 2015, 21 children; Como, June 2015, 37 children and Olomouc, August 2015, 23 children), **70 children** with the **laboratory “Photography and holography”** (Como, 28 children in 2015 and 39 children in 2016), **840 children** with the LuNa Project (<http://luna.dfm.uninsubria.it/>, 340 children in 2015 and 500 in 2016).

Figure 25 Students building an optical apparatus during the International Physics Summer School – Optics (Como, June 2016)

Figure 26 White-light interference obtained with an apparatus built by students during the International Physics Summer School – Optics (Como, June 2016)

Netherlands

Workshop at the Science Centre

At the initiative of the Optics Group of TUD, a room-exhibition with hands-on experiments has been installed in the Science Centre attached to the university. The Science Centre is an open museum for kids and schools to learn more about the science done at the University. Classes visit the Centre for workshops, families as an afternoon adventure.

TUD has built 6 different hands-on experiments with explanations, for ages 8-99 years! University Bachelor students were involved in both the design of the experiments and implementation. Different light concepts were presented with the experiments, such as; polarization, colours, invisibility, index of refraction and illumination.

Those simple concepts were connected with the current research done in the Optics Group of TUD (lighting, colour rendering, cloaking etc.). Brochures, bookmarks and information regarding to TUD's projects were made available, as well as information on the kind of jobs you may have when you study photonics.

The experiments were on display for four months from October 2015 to January 2016, with an average number of 2500 children visiting the centre per month, reaching approximately **10.000 children** during the exhibit.

Figure 27 Hand-on experiments in the Science Center of the Delft University of Technology

9. Summary & evaluation

The activities of 'Children's University' have been evaluated both (1) with respect to *quantitative* expectations with regard to the original proposal and (2) regarding *qualitative* expectations developed during the project.

With more than 3,800 children reached during the project, the expectations concerning the **quantitative Key Performance Indicators were exceeded by almost 10 times** (the target number was defined in the Grant Agreement as our working with 400 children):

Participants in Photonics4All Children's Universities

Figure 1: Participation in Photonics4All children's universities

This large number of events and participants was partially as a result of the unexpected synergy with the International Year of Light in 2015 which provided opportunities for collaborations and partnerships which Photonics4All partners took on enthusiastically, even when they hadn't proposed to work with Children. Once partners had worked with a group of children they had the experience, tools and resources the project had given them to repeat their workshops. The project will have long-term impact as events are now more sustainable, even perhaps without the Photonics4All funding.

The expectations concerning the **qualitative Key Performance Indicators were excelled**. As outlined in the introduction, the generation of impact in the sense of evaluating the impact i.e. "reach x significance" of our events was not planned as the Grant Agreement talks only about "reach". Nevertheless, a qualitative evaluation scheme was developed during the project on the initiative of the project partners. Thanks to the use of various tools, it was possible to see the following change in participant knowledge, attitude and behaviour as follows:

- **Knowledge:** children learned the definition of Photonics and the basic physics behind light and colour, they learned about photonics research and applications in general (e.g. in Germany, Austria and Sweden), and they also learned about careers in Photonics.
- **Attitude:** Students reported on how much they enjoyed themselves at the events, showing engagement to those staffing booths and events

- **Behaviour**: Student attitudes towards further study of Physics and Photonics changed drastically as a response to their Children's University experiences. Their behaviour in the UK will be tracked over the long-term to see if they decide to study physics at University.

Impact on Staff: A precious side-effect of delivering the Children's University events is the learning and skills gained by the University students and staff preparing and delivering the Children's universities. They practiced communication skills – having to explain complex concepts simply, changing their explanations to suit their audience – simple good communication is a valuable skill for presenting work in industry meetings, and for grant writing, those staffing events had to practice their time management and event management skills, and some had to manage staff and budgeting. All of these skills are useful for people who work in photonics research and industry. Many of the lessons learned by the students and staff will be put into practice at future Children's University events. The tools, educational resources and partnerships formed during the events will be repeated long after the end of the Photonics4All project has ended.

Last but not least, the experience gained in this “children's university activity” is gathered as a best practice in our respective handbook (deliverable D4.8).

Appendix 1 – “build your own spectrometer” handout

Spectrometers are an important tool for identifying elements in many scientific applications: build your own spectrometer!

Your spectrometer will use a CD-ROM to split up light into different colours. First, a slice of the CD must be cut out as shown in the plan on the following page (the best way is to use strong scissors or a saw!). **Please only use CDs which are no longer needed!** Print the page with the pattern overleaf on paper or card and cut the pattern along the lines. Cut the inner rectangles out carefully with a sharp knife. When you assemble the spectrometer, be aware that the piece of the CD should be inside the box. It is advisable to tape over the edges and corners with electrical or gaffa tape. Be careful not to tape over the rectangular areas!

Appendix 2 – Handout for the workshops in German

KinderUni Workshop “Licht und Farbe“ mit Frank Reil und Gernot Schaffernak

27. 09. 2016, Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz, Institut für Physik

1) Was ist eigentlich Licht?

Die wichtigste Lichtquelle ist die Sonne, dort entsteht Licht. Auch Glühbirnen können Licht “erzeugen”.

Licht ist sehr schnell, nichts kann sich schneller bewegen als das Licht.

Licht überträgt Informationen:

- In Licht-Leitern (Glasfaser-Kabel) werden E-Mails und Daten um die Welt geleitet.
- Wir können Licht von weit entfernten Sternen studieren und etwas über das Weltall lernen.
- Wir nehmen unsere Umgebung durch Licht wahr, das auf unsere Augen trifft.
- Durch Gesichtsausdrücke und Gesten oder Zeichen können wir uns verständigen.

Licht breitet sich als Welle aus, jede Wellenlänge (in Nano-Meter gemessen) des Lichts entspricht einer Farbe.

er ist 1/1000 von einem Meter. Ein Mikro-Meter ist 1/1000 von einem Milli-Meter.

Ein Nano-Meter (griechisch nanos heißt “Zwerg”) ist 1/1000 von einem Mikro-Meter. Die Wellenberge der Lichtwelle sind ca. 500 Nano-Meter hintereinander (Wellenlänge).

Unsere Augen können drei Wellenlängenbereiche (Farb-Bereiche) wahrnehmen: rot, grün und blau.

Aus diesen Grundfarben kann man alle anderen Farben zusammen mischen.

Wenn alle drei Farben ungefähr im gleichen Verhältnis gemischt werden, mischen sie sich für unsere Augen zu weißem Licht.

Versuch: Additive Farbmischung mit drei einfarbigen LED-Lampen.

Aus weißem Licht kann man mit Farb-Filtern bestimmte Farben herausfiltern (die werden vom Filter absorbiert). Wenn ein Filter blau und grün absorbiert, dann sieht das Licht hinter dem Filter rot aus.

Versuch: Farbfilter am Overhead-Projektor.

Wenn sich Farben so schnell ändern, dass unser Auge sie nicht mehr trennen kann, sehen wir stattdessen die Mischfarbe.

2) Farbzerlegung, Spektroskop

Durch ein Prisma oder ein optisches Linien-Gitter kann Licht in seine Farben zerlegt werden. Das funktioniert, weil unterschiedliche Farben in unterschiedliche Richtungen gebrochen oder gebeugt werden.

Wenn man jetzt noch die Intensität der einzelnen Farben bestimmt, hat man ein Spektrometer.

Damit erkennt man die Unterschiede zwischen einer Glühbirne und einer Energiesparlampe. Die Glühbirne hat ein gleichmäßiges Spektrum, ähnlich der Sonne, während die Energiessparlampe nur mit wenigen Farben leuchtet, die als Linien im Spektrum zu sehen sind.

Versuch: Gitter-Spektrometer und verschiedene Lichtquellen.

Auch eine CD kann das Licht in seine Farben zerlegen, wenn man sie schräg beleuchtet.

Achtung: bei diesen Versuchen niemals direkt in die Sonne sehen, die Intensität ist zu hoch und kann unsere Augen schädigen!

3) Optische Instrumente

Man hat schon in der Antike beobachtet, dass Licht an Wasser-Oberflächen reflektiert wird.

Als man Glas herstellen konnte, fand man heraus, dass das Licht anders durch das Glas läuft (langsamer) als durch Luft. Das Licht wird gebrochen, je nachdem, unter welchem Winkel es in das Glas fällt. Dieser Effekt ist sehr nützlich für verschiedene optische Instrumente.

- Die Lupe: Man kann einen Gegenstand dank der Lupe näher zum Auge bringen, ohne dass er unscharf wird → er wirkt vergrößert! **Versuch:** Einzelne Farb-Pixel am Bildschirm sehen.
- Teleskop: Hilft uns, entfernte Gegenstände zu vergrößern und Licht zu sammeln, damit wir schwach leuchtende Sterne beobachten können. **Versuch:** Bau eines Teleskops mit Linsen.
- Mikroskop: Erzeugt Bilder von den ganz kleinen Dingen. Die Fein-Struktur von

Oberflächen wird sichtbar. **Versuch:** kleine Dinge unter dem Mikroskop.

4) Laser und Beugung

Der Laser ist einfarbig und hat sehr gleichmäßige Lichtwellen. Während bei Glühbirnen die Wellen mit der Entfernung von der Lichtquelle auseinanderlaufen, bleiben die Laserwellen über weite Strecken gleichförmig. Dadurch kann man Licht-Beugung besonders gut untersuchen.

Versuch: Beugung von Laser-Licht am Linien-Gitter.

Der Laser ist gefährlich für unsere Augen, weil die Licht-Intensität höher ist als bei anderen Lichtquellen. Laserlicht kann sehr gut fokussiert werden.

Niemals mit dem Laser ins Auge leuchten! Das Auge kann geschädigt werden!

5) Streuung und Absorption

Sonnenlicht ist weiß, aber weil das blaue Licht in der Atmosphäre gestreut wird, erscheint uns der Himmel blau. Absorption und Streuung vermindern beide die Helligkeit des Lichts. Bei der Absorption wird das Licht verschluckt, bei der Streuung wird es nur umgelenkt.

Versuch: kleine Menge Milch in einem Wasserglas (Beobachtung der Streuung).

6) Schatten und Dunkelheit

Ohne Licht würde es auch keine Schatten geben. Wenn man mit verschiedenen Farben beleuchtet, die sich zu weiß mischen, kann es auch farbige Schatten geben.

Es ist wichtig, dass wir in der Nacht wenig Licht haben, damit wir gut schlafen können. Die Straßenbeleuchtung in der Stadt trägt zur sogenannten "Lichtverschmutzung" bei, die für AstronomInnen, aber auch für jeden beim Einschlafen ein Problem sein kann. Überlege dir, wie man eine Straßenlaterne bauen kann, die nur die Straße beleuchtet, aber nicht die umliegenden Häuser oder den Himmel.

Viel Spaß beim Experimentieren wünschen Frank und Gernot!

Appendix 3 – ‘Mobile Ghost’ Handout for the Workshop in the UK

Mobile Ghosts

By the end of this activity you will have:

- made a “Mobile Ghost”
- learned about reflection and refraction of light
- learned about how we see in three dimensions (3D)

Useful vocabulary: transparent, translucent, opaque, transmit, absorb, reflect and refract.

What is a Mobile Ghost?

More commonly known as Pepper’s Ghost, the ‘mobile ghost’ shown in fig.1. is an optical illusion often used in haunted houses, concerts and head up displays in fighter jet windshields to make an image appear 3D and float in mid-air.

How does it work?

The illusion is formed when rays of light from an object are reflected off one surface onto another reflective surface into our eyes.

If the second reflective surface is transparent, part of the image is reflected and part is transmitted as shown in fig 2. The object appears slightly translucent and seems to float behind the transparent reflective surface.

The ‘Ghosts’ look 3D because we see a slightly different image with both of our eyes.

Our brain combines both views and interprets the object as being three dimensional.

What you need:

- scissors
- acetate sheet with template
- sticky tape
- mobile phone.

Fig.1. Model Kate Moss appearing on stage as a Pepper’s ghost, (2015).

<http://mesmer.co.uk/projects/alexander-mcqueen-va-savage-beauty/>

Fig.2. How Pepper’s Ghost works on Stage.

<http://dip9.aaschool.ac.uk/new-peppers-ghost/>

Instructions

1. Download a ready-made Pepper's Ghost app such as "Hologram Pyramid Videos" from the Google Play store for Android, or the iTunes store for iOS.

Scan the QR code below for a quick link.

<https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/hologram-pyramid-videos/id1100684856?mt=8>

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.holapex.hologram.app&hl=en>

2. Cut out your template by cutting along the dashed lines on the acetate sheet.
3. Fold the template along the solid lines.
4. Tape the folded cut-out into a flat-topped pyramid shape as shown in the diagram on the right.
5. Place your pyramid in the centre of the video and watch from the side!
6. If the floating animated image is difficult to see – turn the lights off in the room, or make sure that the image has a dark background.

The Photonics4All app

Download our free app to find out more about photonics "the science of light". You can learn about things like lasers, reflection and refraction, polarization, colours and much more.

Find it at

https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=esiee.android.nevyan.photonicsforall&hl=en_GB

or search for "Photonics4All" on the Google Play store.

Mobile Ghost Template

